

EOG Controlled Motorized Wheelchair for Disabled Persons

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Abstract : Assistive robotics are playing a vital role in advancing the quality of life for disabled people. There exist wide range of systems that can control and guide autonomous mobile robots. The objective of the control system is to guide an autonomous mobile robot using the movement of eyes by means of EOG signal. The EOG signal is acquired using Ag-AgCl electrodes and this signal is processed by a microcontroller unit to calculate the eye gaze direction. Then according to the guidance control strategy, the control commands of the wheelchair are sent. The classification of different eye movements allows us to generate simple code for controlling the wheelchair. This work was aimed towards developing a usable and low-cost assistive robotic wheel chair system for disabled people. To live more independent life, the system can be used by the handicapped people especially those with only eye-motor coordination.

Keywords : Electrooculography, Microcontroller, Motors, Wheelchair

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